

QUIZ**LAST NAME:** Rivera Vargas**FIRST NAME:** Mariana**PROGRAM CODE:** MBASD**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice 365

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Which of the following statements is not a consequence of plagiarism:

- Gives credit to the authors of the consulted source.¹
- Diminish the credibility of the research/paper.
- Avoids the opportunity of transferring and developing knowledge.
- None of the above.

2. According to Kemper, Meyer and Sebranek 1999, to which thinking level do the following actions correspond: Reshape, connect information, imagine and hypothesize new information

- Recall.

¹ Euclid University, *ACA-401 COURSEPACK PERIOD 1* (Euclid University 2015), 9-11, accessed on 12 November 2019, <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1>

- Evaluate.
- Synthesize.**²
- Apply.

3. **Which of the following sentences is grammatically correct?**

- Based on information collected in books, magazines and podcasts and newspapers.
- The letter was delivered to the US Department of treasury.
- Due to the Industrial Revolution, the rural population moved to this city about two hundred years ago.**³
- It includes Roman and Arabian numerals.

4. **Which of the following options misses a comma?**

- European Court of Auditors, 2019. *History*. Accessed November 9, 2019. <https://www.eca.europa.eu/en/Pages/History.aspx#>.
- In this effort, the ethical dimension is key, and this point appears in the references to the norms of the document.
- It is already arranged mom. Please do not worry about it.**⁴
- The service was slow, the food was cold, and the bill was incorrect.

² Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000: A guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning*, 4th ed. (Wilmington: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 290.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researches*, ed Wayne C. Booth et al., 8th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press), 182.

⁴ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, 405.

5. **If all options are available, which is the correct form to cite a URL?**
- The URL as it appears in the browser.
 - The URL's preferred form along with the citation data for a source.
 - The DOI based URL.⁵**
 - The URL as it appears in the browser enclosed in brackets.
6. **For assuring objectivity in research papers, which of the following actions should be avoided?**
- Use of superlative adjectives.
 - Use of superlative adjectives and personal opinions or beliefs.⁶**
 - Use of superlative adjectives, personal opinions or beliefs, and stating a hypothesis.
 - All of the above.
7. **According to the Harvard Rule of Style, which of the following elements are found in a bibliography list and in a reference list?**
- Consulted sources and presentation format.
 - Consulted sources.
 - Cited sources.
 - Presentation format⁷**

⁵ Turabian, 88.

⁶ Euclid University, *ACA-401 COURSEPACK PERIOD 4*. (Euclid University: 2015), 9-10, accessed on 12 November 2019, <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/YIJXVLgPv0/>

⁷ Euclid University, *ACA-401 COURSEPACK PERIOD 4*, 80.

8. **The following text comes from a proposal for the European Commission: *The EPI and ESI indexes are used for the final reflexion shown in page 15.* How many linguistic mistakes are found in it?**

None.

3.

2.⁸

4.

9. **Which of the following characteristics are found in long quotations?**

They are over 4 lines.

They require no quotation marks.

They are stated in a separate block, indented from the left and with a space above and below the quote.

All of the above.⁹

10. **When using the Author-Data Style, which of the following type of sources may be omitted from the reference list?**

Biblical and other sacred works.

Classical, medieval and early literary works.

Comments published in social media by the President of Bolivia.

2 and 3.¹⁰

⁸ European Commission Directorate-General for Translation, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 7th ed. (European Commission: 2011), 12, accessed November 12, 2019, <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/xitMjHAGfJ/>

⁹ Euclid University, *ACA-401 COURSEPACK PERIOD 4*, 94.

¹⁰ Turabian, 133–34.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.